

Conjunctival Squamous Cell Carcinoma in Situ in a Young Immunocompetent Adult: A Case Report

Frida Monserrath Ortega García, MD¹, Manuel Alejandro Vega Villegas, MD², Themis Gwendolyne Aguilar Arciga, MD³, Víctor Antonio Mendoza Vargas, MD⁴, David Arturo Ancona Lezama, MD, PhD.⁵

¹Instituto de Seguridad y Servicios Sociales de los Trabajadores del Estado, Hospital Regional Valentín Gómez Farías” Internal Medicine Department. Zapopan, Jal, Mexico. (<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-8405-9844>).

²Instituto de Seguridad y Servicios Sociales de los Trabajadores del Estado, Hospital Regional Valentín Gómez Farías” Internal Medicine Department. Zapopan, Jal, Mexico. (<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-8118-6119>).

³Instituto de Seguridad y Servicios Sociales de los Trabajadores del Estado, Hospital Regional Valentín Gómez Farías” Ophthalmology Department. Zapopan, Jal, Mexico. (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5606-1828>).

⁴Instituto de Seguridad y Servicios Sociales de los Trabajadores del Estado, Hospital Regional Valentín Gómez Farías” Internal Medicine Department. Zapopan, Jal, Mexico. (<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-8662-2087>).

⁵“Eye Cancer Institute”. Monterrey, Nuevo León, Mexico. (<https://orcid.org/00000003-2748-9048>).

ABSTRACT

Background: Conjunctival squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) is the most common malignancy of the ocular surface, typically seen in elderly patients with risk factors such as UV exposure, immunosuppression, or HPV infection. Cases in young, immunocompetent individuals are rare.

Case Presentation: We report a 25-year-old healthy female who presented with an asymptomatic conjunctival lesion incidentally identified during routine ophthalmologic evaluation. She underwent complete surgical excision. Histopathology confirmed squamous cell carcinoma in situ with clear margins. Six months after surgery, no recurrence or local invasion was observed.

Conclusion: SCC in situ of the conjunctiva in young patients without typical risk factors is exceptionally uncommon. The nonspecific nature of symptoms can lead to misdiagnosis and a considerable challenge for physicians. Early detection and complete excision offer excellent prognosis. This case emphasizes the importance of routine ocular examination and clinical suspicion, even in low-risk populations.

KEYWORDS: Conjunctival squamous cell carcinoma, ocular surface tumor, carcinoma in situ, ocular oncology, ocular surface squamous neoplasia, conjunctival intraepithelial neoplasm

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
28 July 2025

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

Squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) of the conjunctiva is the most prevalent nonpigmented malignancy of the ocular surface, comprising a spectrum of disease that includes conjunctival intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN), carcinoma in situ (CIS), and invasive SCC [1]. While SCC commonly affects older individuals, its occurrence in young adults is rare and often unexpected.

Major risk factors include cumulative ultraviolet (UV) radiation, human papillomavirus (HPV) infection, HIV related immunosuppression, exposure to chemicals, and

chronic inflammation [2]. However, cases in young, healthy individuals without immunosuppression or environmental exposure are unusual and sparsely reported in the literature. Early diagnosis is critical, as in situ carcinomas are often curable with complete excision and carry a lower risk of local invasion or recurrence [3]. We present a rare case of conjunctival SCC in situ in a young adult woman without known risk factors.

Conjunctival Squamous Cell Carcinoma in Situ in a Young Immunocompetent Adult: A Case Report

CASE REPORT

A 25-year-old female physician, with no personal or family history of malignancy, presented for routine ophthalmological screening. She reported no ocular symptoms, prior trauma, or systemic illness. She had no history of immunosuppression, HPV infection, or extensive sun exposure.

Slit lamp examination revealed a well circumscribed, vascularized lesion located on the nasal bulbar conjunctiva of the right eye, measuring approximately 3 mm in diameter [Fig. 1]. The lesion was clinically suspicious for ocular surface squamous neoplasia (OSSN).

Anterior segment optical coherence tomography (OCT) and ultrasound bio microscopy (UBM) were performed, showing

no evidence of intraocular or adjacent tissue invasion. [Fig. 2]. Initial management included topical interferon alpha-2b 1×10^6 UI/ml 4 times a day for 6 months with no resolution.

Complete excisional biopsy was carried out under surgical microscope, using a no-touch technique with 4mm margins and cryotherapy.

Histopathologic examination revealed a squamous cell carcinoma in situ with preserved basement membrane, full thickness epithelial atypia. Surgical margins were tumor-free.

Follow-up at 1, 3, and 6 months revealed no clinical signs of recurrence or scleral extension.

Figure 1. Vascularized lesion on the nasal bulbar conjunctiva of the right eye

Figure 2. OCT and UBM showed no evidence of further invasion.

DISCUSSION

Conjunctival SCC has an incidence of 0.13-1.9/100 000 per year. The condition is classically associated with UV light exposure, immunodeficiency (especially HIV), and HPV infection, particularly HPV types 16 and 18 [3][4]. The mean age at diagnosis is typically over 60 years, and the disease is uncommon in individuals younger than 30.

Our case is notable due to the age of the patient and absence of risk factors. A handful of similar cases have been described in the literature, often with suspected associations to HPV even in immunocompetent individuals.

The prognosis of conjunctival SCC in situ is excellent when completely excised. Incomplete excision and scleral invasion are predictors of recurrence and metastasis [5]. Adjunctive treatments such as cryotherapy or topical medical management with chemotherapy drugs and

immunomodulatory agents such as 5-fluorouracil, mitomycin C, and interferon alpha-2b may be employed in cases with high-risk features and reduce recurrence up to 0-12.3% [6].

Routine ophthalmologic evaluation remains a cornerstone for early diagnosis, particularly in asymptomatic cases. Clinical suspicion should be maintained even in low-risk patients, especially when encountering conjunctival lesions with atypical features.

CONCLUSION

This case highlights the importance of including conjunctival SCC in situ in the differential diagnosis of ocular surface lesions, even in young and otherwise healthy patients. Surgical excision with histological confirmation ensures accurate diagnosis and reduces risk of recurrence. Early detection and management are key to favorable outcomes.

REFERENCES

- I. Shields, Carol L., et al. “Conjunctival Tumors: Review of Clinical Features, Risks, Biomarkers, and Outcomes— the 2017 J. Donald M. Gass Lecture.” *Asia-Pacific Journal of Ophthalmology*, vol. 6, no. 2, 2017, <https://doi.org/10.22608/apo.201710>
- II. Xie, Bihua, et al. “Exploring the Risk Factors of Conjunctival Squamous Cell Carcinoma and Establishing a Prognostic Model: Retrospective Study.” *Disease Markers*, vol. 2022, Autumn 2022, p. 5427579, <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/5427579>
- III. Sayed-Ahmed, Ibrahim O., et al. “Diagnosis and Medical Management of Ocular Surface Squamous Neoplasia.” *Expert Review of Ophthalmology*, vol. 12, no. 1, 5 Dec. 2016, pp. 11–19, <https://doi.org/10.1080/17469899.2017.1263567>.
- IV. Gichuhi, Stephen, et al. “Pathophysiology of Ocular Surface Squamous Neoplasia.” *Experimental Eye Research*, vol. 129, Dec. 2014, pp. 172–182, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.exer.2014.10.015>.
- V. Höllhumer, Roland, et al. “Ocular Surface Squamous Neoplasia: Management and Outcomes.” *The Royal College of Ophthalmologists*, 9 Feb. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41433-02101422-3>.
- VI. H Y Yeoh, Clarice, et al. “The Management of Ocular Surface Squamous Neoplasia (OSSN).” *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, vol. 24, no. 1, 31 Dec. 2022, pp. 713–713, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24010713>